

IPBES Data Management Tutorials

Chapter 6: Examples of implementing the IPBES data management Policy

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014802](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014802)

Chapter Lead: Rainer M. Krug

Editors: Aidin Niamir

Description of Chapter

This chapter contains examples of how certain data management tasks and workflows were implemented within IPBES so that they follow the data management policy. Over time, diverse examples from different assessments and other IPBES projects will be added.

Overview of Sessions:

Session 6.1: Data management best practices

- Provides a general review of some best practices of data management and what to expect for this chapter
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4018663](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4018663)

Session 6.2: Literature review from the Global Assessment chapter 4

- Walks you through each step of the data management of the systematic literature review from the Chapter 4 of the Global Assessment
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4018667](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4018667)

Suggested citation:

Krug, R. M., Niamir, A. (2020) Chapter 6: Examples of implementing the IPBES data management Policy, in Krug, R. M., Aboki Omare, B. D., Niamir (eds.) IPBES Data Management Tutorials, IPBES Task Force on Knowledge and Data. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014802](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014802)

Contact:

If you have any questions or would like to provide feedback on these sessions please contact the technical support unit on knowledge and data at tsu.data@ipbes.net.